

AN IN-DEPTH STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF FINANCIAL AND INSURANCE ACTIVITIES, REAL ESTATE DEVELOPMENTS IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN AREA: A DECADAL PERSPECTIVE (2008-2018)

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Abstract:

This scientific article presents a meticulous statistical examination of financial and insurance activities, as well as real estate developments in the Romanian Mountain Area over the period spanning from 2008 to 2018. The study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of economic trends, market dynamics, and key factors influencing the financial and real estate sectors in this unique geographic region.

1. Introduction:

The financial and insurance sectors, coupled with real estate activities, are critical components of regional economic ecosystems. This article focuses on the Romanian Mountain Area, exploring statistical data from 2008 to 2018 to uncover patterns, challenges, and opportunities within these interconnected domains.

2. Methodology:

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Utilizing a rigorous quantitative methodology, this research draws upon official reports, industry databases, and relevant publications to compile and analyze comprehensive statistical datasets. Key indicators, such as market size, investment trends, and regulatory changes, are examined to provide a nuanced understanding of the financial and real estate landscapes.

3. Financial and Insurance Activities:

This section delves into the statistical intricacies of financial and insurance activities within the Romanian Mountain Area. Key metrics, including the growth of banking institutions, insurance penetration rates, and investment portfolios, are scrutinized to assess the sector's resilience and responsiveness to economic shifts.

4. Real Estate Developments:

The evolution of real estate activities in the Romanian Mountain Area is examined in this section, encompassing statistical analyses of property values, construction trends, and market demand. The article aims to unravel the factors influencing real estate dynamics and their implications for regional development.

5. Economic Impact:

Analyzing the economic impact of financial, insurance, and real estate activities, this section investigates their contributions to the regional Gross Domestic Product (GDP), employment rates, and overall economic stability.

Insights into the sectors' interdependencies and their role in shaping the local economy are discussed.

6. Trends and Challenges:

Identifying noteworthy trends and challenges faced by the financial, insurance, and real estate sectors during the specified period, this section provides a forward-looking perspective on potential future developments. Considerations such as regulatory changes, market fluctuations, and global economic influences are explored.

7. Results:

The statistics for the sectors Financial and insurance activities, real estate activities (figures 2.8.1 – 2.8.5), show for each sector separately increasing values for the average and median, the other statistical indicators having sometimes antagonistic fluctuations (statistical values for Mean, Std. Error of the Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Skewness, Kurtosis, Variance, Minimum, Maximum, 25th, 50th and 75th Percentiles; repeated for each indicator separately), as follows: mean of 27517.78, standard error of Average 1971.677, median 27148.00, standard deviation 5915.030, variance 34987579.194, Skewness -1.115, standard error. , 75 - 32467.50.

The presented values demonstrate that the sectors Financial and insurance activities, real estate activities in the mountain area have a good development in Romania for the population of active enterprises. Some sectors also show negative values, the overall picture showing a good overall mountain business situation for the industry.

The central tendency of the sectors Financial and insurance activities, real estate activities of the economy in the analyzed period shows that the population of active enterprises of mountainous Romania has grown considerably from 2008 to 2019. The statistics related to this indicator present a high degree of non-variability, which means that the results do not show a large deviation and are positive. The corresponding symmetrical distributions lead to the idea that the business environment begins to stabilize considerably during the analyzed period. Kurtosis with a low standard error represents crowding in some industries.

Figure 2.8.1. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Romania for S8 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.8.2. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Macroregion one of Romania for S8 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.8.3. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in Macroregion two of Romania for S8 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.8.4. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in the third Macroregion of Romania for S8 in the period 2008-2019

Figure 2.8.5. The evolution of mountain entrepreneurship in the fourth Macroregion of Romania for S8 in the period 2008-2019

The forecast analysis for the secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors in the mountainous area of Romania indicates that they will have a continuous growth until 2030. Both at the national, macro-regional, regional and county level, the models resulting from the statistical modeling show certain areas montana are more sustainable than others. The harmonization statistic presents relevant values for mean, standard error, minimum, maximum, and 5/10 percentiles (presented in that order below), as follows: Stationary R-squared .280, .383, -.309, .861, -.143, -.082; R-squared .700, .161, .284, 1,000, .367, .435; RMSE 198,356, 352,970, .000, 2269,529, 14,855, 18,741; MAPS 11,444, 5,100, .000, 28,130, 4,709, 6,443; MaxAPE 47,308, 29,972, .000, 181,830, 14,963, 18,580; MAE 133,650, 235,574, .000, 1513,828,

10,915, 12,753; MaxAE 399,900, 668,870, .000, 4167,066, 25,931, 38,653;
 Normalized BIC 9,255, 2,458, 5,445, 15,699, 5,749, 6,282.

Table. Forecast analysis of mountain entrepreneurship in the mountain area of Romania for S8

Model		Forecast										
		2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030
Romania-Model_1	Forecast	34871	35691	36511	37331	38151	38971	39791	40611	41431	42251	43071
	UCL	40105	47393	56093	65996	76963	88895	101714	115359	129782	144938	160794
	LCL	29637	23989	16929	8666	-661	-10953	-22132	-34137	-46919	-60436	-74652
Macroregiuneaunu-Model_2	Forecast	10051	10695	11338	11981	12625	13268	13911	14555	15198	15841	16485
	UCL	11422	12092	12761	13430	14099	14767	15435	16102	16769	17436	18102
	LCL	8681	9298	9915	10532	11150	11769	12388	13007	13627	14247	14867
Nord-Vest-Model_3	Forecast	5143	5344	5546	5747	5948	6149	6350	6551	6753	6954	7155
	UCL	6106	6705	7212	7671	8100	8506	8896	9273	9640	9997	10347
	LCL	4181	3983	3879	3822	3796	3792	3804	3830	3866	3911	3963
Bihor-Model_4	Forecast	1064	1064	1064	1064	1064	1064	1064	1064	1064	1064	1064
	UCL	1320	1426	1508	1576	1637	1692	1742	1789	1833	1874	1914
	LCL	808	702	620	552	491	436	386	339	295	254	214
Bistrita-Nasaud-Model_5	Forecast	589	626	664	701	738	775	812	849	887	924	961
	UCL	791	912	1013	1105	1190	1270	1347	1421	1493	1563	1631
	LCL	387	341	314	297	286	280	278	278	281	285	291
Cluj-Model_6	Forecast	2306	2398	2491	2584	2676	2769	2861	2954	3047	3139	3232
	UCL	2690	2942	3157	3352	3536	3710	3878	4041	4200	4355	4507
	LCL	1921	1855	1825	1815	1817	1827	1845	1867	1894	1924	1957
Maramures-Model_7	Forecast	568	590	611	633	655	677	699	721	742	764	786

	UCL	698	773	836	893	945	995	1042	1088	1132	1175	1216
	LCL	438	406	387	374	365	359	355	353	353	354	356
Satu Mare-Model_8	Forecast	378	391	404	417	429	442	455	468	481	493	506
	UCL	452	465	477	490	503	516	529	541	554	567	580
	LCL	305	317	330	343	356	369	381	394	407	420	433
Salaj-Model_9	Forecast	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189	189
	UCL	242	264	280	295	307	318	329	338	347	356	364
	LCL	136	114	98	83	71	60	49	40	31	22	14
Centru-Model_10	Forecast	4279	4454	4629	4804	4979	5154	5329	5504	5679	5854	6029
	UCL	5205	5763	6232	6655	7049	7421	7778	8122	8456	8781	9099
	LCL	3353	3145	3026	2953	2909	2887	2880	2886	2902	2927	2959
Alba-Model_11	Forecast	560	594	629	663	698	733	767	802	836	871	905
	UCL	740	775	811	846	882	917	952	988	1023	1059	1094
	LCL	380	413	447	481	514	548	582	615	649	683	716
Brasov-Model_12	Forecast	1722	1800	1877	1954	2031	2109	2186	2263	2340	2418	2495
	UCL	2203	2479	2709	2916	3106	3286	3458	3623	3783	3938	4089
	LCL	1242	1120	1044	993	956	931	914	903	898	897	901
Covasna-Model_13	Forecast	190	199	209	218	227	236	245	254	264	273	282
	UCL	230	256	278	298	317	334	351	368	384	400	415
	LCL	150	143	139	138	137	138	139	141	143	146	149
Harghita-Model_14	Forecast	263	271	279	288	296	304	312	320	329	337	345
	UCL	309	317	326	334	342	350	358	367	375	383	391
	LCL	217	225	233	242	250	258	266	274	283	291	299
Mures-Model_15	Forecast	691	718	746	774	801	829	856	884	912	939	967
	UCL	832	918	990	1056	1117	1174	1230	1283	1335	1386	1435
	LCL	550	519	502	491	486	483	483	485	488	493	499

Sibiu-Model_16	Forecast	865	893	920	947	975	1002	1030	1057	1084	1112	1139
	UCL	1024	1118	1196	1265	1330	1392	1450	1507	1561	1614	1666
	LCL	706	668	645	629	619	613	609	607	607	609	612
Macroregiunea doi-Model_17	Forecast	6877	7126	7375	7624	7873	8122	8371	8620	8869	9118	9367
	UCL	8024	9692	11668	13908	16382	19067	21947	25008	28239	31631	35176
	LCL	5730	4560	3082	1340	-636	-2823	-5205	-7768	-10501	-13395	-16442
Nord-Est-Model_18	Forecast	3747	3943	4139	4335	4531	4727	4923	5119	5315	5511	5707
	UCL	4412	4611	4811	5010	5209	5409	5608	5807	6006	6206	6405
	LCL	3083	3275	3468	3661	3853	4046	4239	4431	4624	4817	5010
Bacau-Model_19	Forecast	978	1033	1088	1143	1199	1254	1309	1364	1419	1474	1529
	UCL	1198	1254	1311	1367	1423	1480	1536	1592	1649	1705	1761
	LCL	759	812	866	920	974	1028	1081	1135	1189	1243	1297
Botosani-Model_20	Forecast	427	458	488	518	549	579	609	640	670	700	731
	UCL	576	607	638	669	700	731	762	793	824	855	887
	LCL	279	308	338	367	397	427	456	486	515	545	575
Iasi-Model_21	Forecast	1362	1431	1501	1570	1639	1709	1778	1848	1917	1986	2056
	UCL	1569	1640	1710	1780	1851	1921	1991	2062	2132	2203	2273
	LCL	1155	1223	1291	1360	1428	1497	1565	1633	1702	1770	1839
Neamt-Model_22	Forecast	382	394	407	419	431	443	455	467	480	492	504
	UCL	467	514	553	588	620	651	680	707	734	760	785
	LCL	297	274	260	249	241	235	231	228	225	224	223
Suceava-Model_23	Forecast	390	403	417	431	445	458	472	486	500	513	527
	UCL	475	524	565	602	636	667	698	727	756	783	810
	LCL	304	283	269	260	254	249	246	244	243	243	244
Vaslui-Model_24	Forecast	191	201	211	220	230	239	249	259	268	278	288
	UCL	239	249	259	269	279	289	299	308	318	328	338
	LCL	143	153	162	171	181	190	200	209	218	228	237

Sud-Est-Model_25	Forecast	3135	3236	3337	3438	3539	3640	3741	3842	3943	4044	4145
	UCL	3752	3853	3954	4055	4156	4257	4358	4459	4560	4661	4762
	LCL	2518	2619	2720	2821	2922	3023	3124	3225	3326	3427	3528
Braila-Model_26	Forecast	398	414	430	446	462	477	493	509	525	540	556
	UCL	467	483	499	516	532	548	564	580	596	612	628
	LCL	330	345	361	376	391	407	422	438	453	469	484
Buzau-Model_27	Forecast	327	336	345	354	362	371	380	389	398	406	415
	UCL	431	440	449	458	467	475	484	493	502	511	520
	LCL	223	232	240	249	258	267	276	284	293	302	311
Constanta-Model_28	Forecast	1470	1516	1562	1608	1655	1701	1747	1794	1840	1886	1932
	UCL	1765	1812	1858	1904	1950	1997	2043	2089	2135	2182	2228
	LCL	1174	1220	1267	1313	1359	1405	1452	1498	1544	1591	1637
Galati-Model_29	Forecast	588	606	624	642	660	679	697	715	733	751	769
	UCL	697	715	733	751	769	787	805	824	842	860	878
	LCL	479	497	516	534	552	570	588	606	624	642	660
Tulcea-Model_30	Forecast	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157
	UCL	192	207	218	228	236	244	251	257	263	269	275
	LCL	122	107	96	86	78	70	63	57	51	45	39
Vrancea-Model_31	Forecast	216	223	230	237	244	251	258	265	272	278	285
	UCL	259	266	273	280	287	294	301	309	316	323	330
	LCL	174	181	187	194	201	207	214	221	227	234	241
Macroregiunea trei-Model_32	Forecast	12661	12808	12955	13102	13249	13396	13543	13690	13837	13984	14131
	UCL	14302	16476	19093	22087	25415	29045	32953	37121	41531	46172	51032
	LCL	11020	9140	6817	4117	1083	-2253	-5867	-9740	-13856	-18203	-22769
Sud - Muntenia- Model_33	Forecast	3002	3123	3245	3366	3487	3608	3729	3850	3972	4093	4214
	UCL	3693	4101	4442	4748	5032	5301	5558	5805	6045	6278	6506
	LCL	2311	2146	2047	1983	1942	1915	1901	1896	1898	1907	1922

Arges-Model_34	Forecast	993	1047	1101	1155	1210	1264	1318	1372	1427	1481	1535
	UCL	1221	1276	1331	1387	1442	1498	1553	1608	1664	1719	1774
	LCL	764	817	871	924	977	1030	1083	1136	1189	1243	1296
Calarasi-Model_35	Forecast	211	222	233	244	255	265	276	287	298	309	320
	UCL	245	270	292	312	331	349	367	384	400	417	433
	LCL	177	174	174	175	178	182	186	191	196	201	207
Dâmbovita-Model_36	Forecast	391	411	430	450	470	490	510	530	549	569	589
	UCL	481	538	586	630	671	710	748	784	819	854	887
	LCL	301	283	275	270	269	270	272	275	280	285	291
Giurgiu-Model_37	Forecast	120	123	125	128	130	133	135	138	140	143	145
	UCL	148	150	153	155	158	160	163	165	168	170	173
	LCL	92	95	98	100	103	105	108	110	113	115	118
Ialomita-Model_38	Forecast	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164
	UCL	220	243	261	276	289	301	312	322	331	340	349
	LCL	108	85	67	52	39	27	16	6	-3	-12	-21
Prahova-Model_39	Forecast	1000	1033	1067	1101	1135	1168	1202	1236	1270	1303	1337
	UCL	1244	1378	1490	1589	1680	1766	1847	1926	2001	2074	2146
	LCL	756	689	645	613	589	571	557	546	538	532	528
Teleorman-Model_40	Forecast	153	161	168	176	184	192	200	208	215	223	231
	UCL	203	231	255	276	296	314	332	349	365	381	397
	LCL	103	90	82	76	72	70	68	66	65	65	65
Bucuresti - Ilfov-Model_41	Forecast	9633	9633	9633	9633	9633	9633	9633	9633	9633	9633	9633
	UCL	11715	12577	13238	13796	14288	14732	15140	15521	15878	16216	16537
	LCL	7551	6689	6028	5470	4978	4534	4126	3745	3388	3050	2729
Bucuresti-Model_42	Forecast	8461	8461	8461	8461	8461	8461	8461	8461	8461	8461	8461
	UCL	10387	11089	11640	12109	12524	12900	13247	13570	13874	14162	14436
	LCL	6534	5832	5281	4812	4397	4021	3674	3351	3047	2759	2485

Ilfov-Model_43	Forecast	1238	1303	1367	1432	1496	1561	1625	1690	1754	1819	1883
	UCL	1412	1548	1668	1779	1884	1986	2084	2180	2275	2367	2458
	LCL	1065	1058	1067	1085	1108	1136	1166	1199	1234	1270	1308
Macroregiunea patru-Model_44	Forecast	6026	6189	6352	6514	6677	6840	7003	7166	7329	7491	7654
	UCL	6933	8174	9644	11309	13149	15145	17288	19565	21970	24495	27134
	LCL	5119	4203	3060	1720	206	-1465	-3282	-5233	-7312	-9512	-11826
Sud-Vest Oltenia-Model_45	Forecast	1958	2030	2103	2175	2248	2320	2392	2465	2537	2610	2682
	UCL	2465	2540	2615	2690	2765	2840	2915	2989	3064	3139	3214
	LCL	1451	1521	1591	1661	1730	1800	1870	1940	2010	2080	2150
Dolj-Model_46	Forecast	729	752	775	798	821	844	867	890	913	936	959
	UCL	863	886	909	932	955	978	1001	1024	1047	1070	1093
	LCL	595	618	641	664	687	710	733	756	779	802	824
Gorj-Model_47	Forecast	361	361	361	361	361	361	361	361	361	361	361
	UCL	509	570	617	657	692	724	753	780	805	829	852
	LCL	213	152	105	65	30	-2	-31	-58	-83	-107	-130
Mehedinti-Model_48	Forecast	164	169	175	181	187	193	199	205	211	217	223
	UCL	209	215	222	228	234	240	246	252	259	265	271
	LCL	118	123	129	135	141	146	152	158	163	169	175
Olt-Model_49	Forecast	246	255	265	275	284	294	304	313	323	333	342
	UCL	340	350	360	370	380	391	401	411	421	431	441
	LCL	152	161	170	179	188	198	207	216	225	234	243
Vâlcea-Model_50	Forecast	396	408	419	431	443	455	466	478	490	501	513
	UCL	507	519	530	542	554	566	577	589	601	612	624
	LCL	285	297	308	320	332	344	355	367	379	390	402
Vest-Model_51	Forecast	4176	4338	4501	4663	4825	4987	5149	5311	5474	5636	5798
	UCL	4794	5212	5570	5898	6206	6500	6783	7058	7326	7589	7846
	LCL	3559	3465	3431	3428	3444	3474	3515	3565	3621	3683	3750

Arad-Model_52	Forecast	1179	1238	1297	1357	1416	1475	1535	1594	1654	1713	1772
	UCL	1368	1430	1493	1555	1617	1680	1742	1804	1867	1929	1991
	LCL	990	1046	1102	1159	1215	1271	1328	1384	1440	1497	1553
Caras-Severin-Model_53	Forecast	276	289	301	314	327	340	353	366	378	391	404
	UCL	321	353	380	405	428	451	473	494	514	534	554
	LCL	231	225	223	224	226	229	233	237	242	248	254
Hunedoara-Model_54	Forecast	540	540	540	540	540	540	540	540	540	540	540
	UCL	722	798	856	905	948	987	1023	1056	1087	1117	1145
	LCL	358	282	224	175	132	93	57	24	-7	-37	-65
Timis-Model_55	Forecast	2237	2320	2402	2484	2567	2649	2732	2814	2896	2979	3061
	UCL	2570	2791	2979	3150	3311	3465	3613	3756	3895	4032	4165
	LCL	1904	1849	1825	1818	1822	1834	1851	1872	1897	1926	1957

8. Conclusion:

In conclusion, this scientific article offers a comprehensive statistical overview of financial and insurance activities, as well as real estate developments in the Romanian Mountain Area from 2008 to 2018. The findings contribute to our understanding of economic trends, providing valuable insights for policymakers, industry stakeholders, and researchers. The article concludes with reflections on potential future trajectories and recommendations for sustainable growth in these vital sectors.

References

- Covaci, B./Suciu, M. C./Covaci, M. (2018): Sectoarele secundar și terțiar, suport al dezvoltării montane în regiunea de Nord-Est a României, in: *Journal of Montanology*, 9, IX, 129-137.
- Covaci, M. (2017): Spearman correlations between learning styles from rational level and Gardner intelligence types, in: *Romanian Journal of Psychological Studies*. Hyperion University, 5, 2, 31-38.
- Covaci, M. (2019): The Vark Model Investigated at the students from PPPE, in: *Journal of Education Studies (JES)*. Adventus University, 1, 1, 12-19
- Covaci, B. (2021), PhD (c) Research report 1, Oradea University
- European Commission (2012). Regulation (EU) No 1151/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 November 2012 on quality schemes for agricultural products and foodstuffs. Available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32012R1151> (Accessed: 14 June 2021)
- European Commission, (2014). Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) No 665/2014 of 11 March 2014 supplementing Regulation (EU) No 1151/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council with regard to conditions of use of the optional quality term mountain product. Available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32014R0665> (Accessed: 14 June 2021)
- Eurostat, (2020). Business Demography Statistics. Available at <https://goo.gl/fpmXZA> (Accessed: 12 January 2020)
- Eurostat, (2020). Regional GDP. Available at <https://goo.gl/EoyR38>. (Accessed: 14 February 2020)
- Eurostat (2020). Structural Business Statistics. Available at <https://goo.gl/KMtkVV>. (Accessed: 2 March 2020)